

The Current Situation of Sino-Vietnamese Vocabulary Usage Ability among Thai Nguyen High School Students in Thai Nguyen Province, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT: Our study presents the results of a survey on the current situation of Sino-Vietnamese vocabulary usage among 150 students at Thai Nguyen High School. Using a mixed survey method (quantitative and qualitative), the study assessed three core competencies, including identifying, interpreting, and using Sino-Vietnamese vocabulary. The research results show that students' abilities are currently at a fairly good level, with clear differentiation between grade levels. The study also points out systemic limitations in understanding the deep meaning and applying words in context, thereby proposing directions for innovative teaching methods to improve the effectiveness of learning and using this vocabulary class.

KEYWORDS: Sino-Vietnamese vocabulary; identification ability; interpreting ability; usage ability; high school students; Thai Nguyen High School.

1. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In the Vietnamese vocabulary system, Sino-Vietnamese vocabulary plays a crucial role in creating formality, conciseness, and precision in the language. However, mastering this vocabulary requires learners not only to have memorization skills but also the ability to analyze structure and understand nuances of meaning in each specific context. Surveying the current use of Sino-Vietnamese vocabulary by high school students in Thai Nguyen is a key step in establishing a system of practical arguments, serving as a scientific foundation for proposing feasible pedagogical solutions to help students improve their communication and text creation skills.

2. CONTENT

2.1. Survey design

The study was conducted on 150 students (50 students from each of grades 10, 11, and 12) at Thai Nguyen High School using stratified random sampling. The survey tool was a mixed questionnaire:

Quantitative section: Measuring the ability to recognize and understand meaning through an objective test system.

Qualitative section: Assessing the depth of linguistic thinking and the ability to apply vocabulary in practice through essay questions.

2.2. Survey results

The survey results show that students' ability to recognize words is better than their ability to understand their deeper meanings.

Regarding recognition ability, the majority of students master common Sino-Vietnamese vocabulary (e.g., learning, education, compassion) and can distinguish Sino-Vietnamese words from purely Vietnamese words. However, at the structural level, students still have difficulty analyzing the constituent elements of complex words (e.g., the word "unity"). Students' current linguistic thinking is mainly based on intuition and habit rather than analysis based on word structure.

Regarding understanding meaning, students grasp words with moral and social values well, but their understanding is superficial. Their understanding often stops at rote memorization or contextual inference instead of grasping the root word (the Sino-Vietnamese element). As a consequence, students frequently make errors in word usage (such as misusing the word "suspicious" in a positive context) and struggle to distinguish between pairs of synonyms with different nuances of expression (such as "father" - "paternal father," "death" - "passed away"). Although a small number of students possess logical analytical thinking skills (such as the word "altruism"), overall, learning remains fragmented, unsystematic, and not connected to practical application.

Table 2.1. Levels of ability to recognize and understand the meaning of Sino-Vietnamese vocabulary across 3 grades

Grade	Good (%)	Averagh (%)	Weak (%)
10	18%	52%	30%
11	28%	50%	22%
12	40%	45%	15%

Grade 10: The majority are at an average level (52%), while the percentage of weak students remains high (30%). Students mainly rely on foundational knowledge from junior high school, and their ability to analyze vocabulary is still weak.

Grade 11: There is improvement (the percentage of good students increased to 28%), but the average group still accounts for the largest proportion (50%). Students are beginning to be aware of differentiating word classes, but understanding meaning still relies heavily on memorization.

Grade 12: The highest percentage of good students is 40%, and the lowest percentage is weak students (15%). This progress reflects a long-term accumulation process; however, 45% are still at an average level, indicating that the majority of students have not yet reached a deep understanding and flexible application level.

2.3. General assessment and solution orientation

In summary, although the learning process at school has had a positive impact at each grade level, students' language proficiency in Sino-Vietnamese vocabulary is still not truly solid. This situation requires a reform of teaching methods in the following directions:

Emphasis on structural analysis: Helping students understand the root nature of words to deduce meaning.

Clarifying expressive nuances: Training skills in distinguishing synonyms and using words in specific contexts.

Promoting practice: Increasing activities in text creation to help students effectively master Sino-Vietnamese vocabulary in communication and academics.

3. CONCLUSION

The survey results have confirmed that limitations in deeply understanding the original meaning and expressive nuances are major obstacles to students' ability to create quality texts, providing the necessary practical basis for proposing feasible pedagogical solutions in subsequent studies.

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